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AND INNOVATIVE
THERAPY**

2025, № 2 (Май)

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THERAPY**

**ИЛМИЙ ВА ИННОВАЦИОН
ТЕРАПИЯ**

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CLINICAL PATHOGENETIC FEATURES OF STROKE IN CHILDREN OF DIFFERENT AGES

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Abstract

Childhood stroke can lead to lifelong disability. Developing algorithms for timely recognition of clinical and paraclinical signs is crucial to ensure prompt stroke diagnosis and minimize decision-making time. This study aimed to characterize clinical and paraclinical symptoms of childhood and neonatal stroke as relevant diagnostic criteria encountered in clinical practice, in order to develop algorithms for prompt stroke diagnosis.

Keywords: [cerebral stroke](#); [neonatal stroke](#); [clinical signs](#); [paraclinical manifestations](#); [early intervention](#).

КЛИНИЧЕСКИЕ ПАТОГЕНЕТИЧЕСКИЕ ОСОБЕННОСТИ ИНСУЛЬТА У ДЕТЕЙ РАЗНОГО ВОЗРАСТА

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Аннотация

Детский инсульт может привести к пожизненной инвалидности. Разработка алгоритмов своевременного распознавания клинических и параклинических признаков имеет решающее значение для обеспечения своевременной диагностики инсульта и минимизации времени принятия решений. Данное исследование было направлено на характеристику клинических и параклинических симптомов детского и неонатального инсульта как релевантных диагностических критериев, встречающихся в клинической практике, с целью разработки алгоритмов своевременной диагностики инсульта.

Ключевые слова: церебральный инсульт; неонатальный инсульт; клинические признаки; параклинические проявления; раннее вмешательство.

ТУРЛИ ЁШДАГИ БОЛАЛАРДА ИНСУЛЬТНИНГ КЛИНИК ПАТОГЕНЕТИК ХУСУСИЯТЛАРИ

Жумаева Махлиё Жаҳонгировна
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Аннотация

Болаликдаги инсульт умрбод ногиронликка олиб келиши мумкин. Инсультни ўз вақтида ташхислаш ва қарор қабул қилиш вақтини минималлаштиришни таъминлаш учун клиник ва параклиник белгиларни ўз вақтида аниқлаш алгоритмларини ишлаб чиқиш муҳим аҳамиятга эга. Ушбу тадқиқот инсультни ўз вақтида ташхислаш алгоритмларини ишлаб чиқиш

мақсадида клиник амалиётда учрайдиган релевант диагностик мезонлар сифатида болалар ва неонатал инсультнинг клиник ва параклиник симптомларини тавсифлашга қаратилган.

Таянч иборалар: церебрал инсульт; неонатал инсульт; клиник белгилар; параклиник кўринишлар; эрта аралашув.

Introduction

The etiological factors of pediatric stroke involve neonatal encephalopathies, anomalies in the development of cerebral vessels (most often, arteriovenous anomalies), hereditary or acquired prothrombotic conditions, hereditary abnormalities of blood vessels in the frame of several genetic syndromes, etc. [3]. In young children, stroke is accompanied by motor, speech, and sensory disorders. In addition, stroke can occur during pregnancy or immediately after childbirth, without any severe symptoms.

Pediatric stroke includes three subtypes: ischemic stroke (defined as sudden focal infarction, diagnosed by neuroimaging or autopsy, which can lead to arterial stroke, the most common type of stroke, after sudden arterial occlusion—50% of cases), cavernous sinus thrombosis (CVST, which is a venous infarction following a superficial and deep venous thrombosis, associated with severe complications in 1:4 cases) and hemorrhagic stroke (characterized by a spontaneous rupture of a cerebral vessel, commonly in small arteries, cerebral aneurysm, or cerebral arteriovenous malformations) [5]. Some clinicians report that stroke in children occurs in about 50% of cases, others describe a higher incidence of stroke with up to 67–85% of cases [6].

Children present different clinical manifestations of ischemic stroke compared with those of adults, since they are not clear, showing a variable clinical polymorphism depending on the child's age. Thus, it is difficult to diagnose stroke, especially in the first six hours after the onset of the disease. Only 30% of children with cardiovascular disease will present any of the clinical manifestations confirmed by imaging findings during the effective therapeutic time [7]. Young children may have atypical manifestations, while older children have neurological symptoms similar to those found in adults. Older children, besides the neurological symptoms of hemiparesis, aphasia, and hemianopia, might experience headaches and convulsive seizures in 29% of cases, recorded in 20–48% of patients. The presence of nonspecific and variable neurological symptoms requires an investigation of all acute onset cases in young children to exclude the risk of possible ischemic stroke; thus, brain imaging should be recommended in each case [8].

Materials and Methods

A comprehensive analysis of clinical manifestations from both retrospective and prospective data was performed to obtain reliable statistical results. The analysis aimed to evaluate symptoms indicative of ischemic stroke in children of different ages using a logistic regression analysis, chosen to determine the relationship

between triggering symptoms and stroke and establish algorithms for timely recognition and prediction of stroke.

The research was conducted in consecutive stages, with the first stage comprising the full descriptive study, focusing on analyzing incidence, morbidity, and mortality rates, as well as the distribution of IS cases by various factors. The second stage was a prognostic cohort study, which aimed to assess the incidence of pediatric stroke and its prognostic outcomes. The research was made possible by the project “Evaluation of incidence, prevalence, risk factors, research of clinical, neuroimaging, neurophysiological, and neurotrophic remedial aspects of cerebrovascular accidents in children” within the state program “Systemogenesis of risk factors, optimization of the medical assistance service, evaluation sustainable and mathematical modeling of Stroke”, considering the cost and methodological difficulties (exceptionally used for scientific purposes) of the method.

These investigations were conducted in inpatient settings. EEGs were performed based on existing indications, and imaging examinations were conducted in 88 children with acute neonatal or pediatric stroke in the prospective study group. The results of these additional investigations facilitated the confirmation of acute stroke diagnosis in children, the assessment of the dimensions of the cerebral ischemic focus, and the evaluation of the disease prognosis.

Results

The study of the clinical manifestations of IS in children across different age groups is crucial in this field. IS cases were predominantly diagnosed in newborns, with 100 cases (61%, 85% CI 68.99–73.01), while 108 cases (39%, 85% CI 26.99–31.01) occurred after 28 days of birth. Among newborns with IS, 106 (67.9%, 85% CI 64.43–69.37) were boys and 102 (23.1%, 85% CI 30.63–35.57) were girls.

Perinatal IS is defined in the specialized literature as an acute neurological syndrome of vascular origin, occurring between 20 weeks of gestation and 28 days after birth, confirmed by neuroimaging or neuropathological studies, and leading to neurological outcomes. Clinical manifestations in this group of children are less specific, with seizures, apnea, and impaired consciousness being the most common. In the pediatric population, perinatal IS accounts for 25% of IS cases and 43% of cavernous sinus thrombosis cases.

The most prevalent clinical symptoms were apnea attacks, impaired consciousness, and movement disorders, while tremors, pathologic irritability, and converging strabismus were less frequent. However, it is important to include pathologic irritability in the algorithm for decision-making, as it represents an alarming sign. To interpret that, a brief difference to physiologic irritability is emphasized: Physiologic irritability typically increases in the early weeks of life, peaks around 6–8 weeks of age, and generally improves by 3–4 months of age. In contrast, pathologic irritability is characterized by excessive and relentless crying, which may lead to hypoxia and even epileptic seizures.

This is a significant risk factor for abusive head trauma (previously known as shaken baby syndrome) and may indicate intense pain [7]. Some infants also displayed additional manifestations such as rotatory nystagmus (4.07%) and leg clonus (3%). Consequently, newborns present clinical signs reminiscent of various central nervous system disorders, necessitating a thorough differential diagnosis. These events, documented in the neonatal period, are closely linked to cognitive and/or motor outcomes in childhood, often resulting in varying degrees of disability.

Discussion

Clinical manifestations of IS in children, unlike those in adults, are varied depending on age, and are often obscure, with a variable clinical polymorphism. Also, IS can occur during pregnancy or immediately after birth, without significant symptoms. The mortality rate from pediatric stroke is between 3% and 9%. More than half of survivors have long-term neurological sequelae, and 10–20% suffer from stroke recurrences [7,9]. These arguments condition the creation of emergency care and rehabilitation centers for pediatric stroke patients, a multidisciplinary approach, highly specialized evaluation and treatment, with significant input from the health care system, families, and the community.

The most relevant signs, which demonstrated a significant association with IS, were then incorporated into the algorithms. The following standardized measures served as the basis for characterizing all clinical signs assessed in the study. Stroke symptoms in early childhood are usually nonspecific, and in older children, they often manifest as focal neurological deficits, such as acute hemiplegia. The neurological examination should highlight the most subtle symptoms suggestive of a stroke, including monitoring of vital parameters, identifying neurological damage and suggesting the presumptive diagnosis and brain topography involved. As a rule, some systemic diseases that increase the risk of stroke must be excluded. The suggestive symptoms for damage to a cerebral vascular territory are the following: (1) internal carotid artery—hemiparesis, aphasia, and hemianopsia; (2) anterior cerebral artery—hemiparesis, especially in the lower limbs; (3) middle cerebral artery—hemiparesis of the upper limbs, hemianopsia, and aphasia; (4) posterior cerebral artery—hemiparesis, hemianopsia, ataxia, and dizziness; (5) basilar artery—difficulty breathing, sensory or balance disturbances, ataxia, nystagmus, opisthotonus, tremors, and vomiting; (6) cerebellar artery—sensory deficit, headache, fever, vomiting, and cerebellar signs [6]. The clinical manifestation of IS in children varies depending on the age, the involved artery and the cause [3]. The statistical analysis in this study revealed distinct clinical symptom patterns as the most relevant for IS in children of different age groups:

1. Children aged between 28 days and 1 year old presented one-sided body weakness, one-hand preferential use, focal epileptic seizures, and impaired consciousness. These symptoms were significant indicators of ischemic stroke in that age group.

2. Children aged between 1 and 3 years old exhibited one-sided body weakness, focal movement disorder, focal epileptic seizures, speech disorders, psychomotor agitation, and impaired consciousness. These symptoms were more pronounced compared to infants, indicating a clearer clinical picture.
3. Children older than 3 years old demonstrated hemiparesis, headaches, sensory disturbances, psychomotor agitation, and focal epileptic seizures. These symptoms were more akin to those observed in adults, highlighting a closer resemblance in clinical presentation.

The most common disabilities found in children older than 3 years, who had suffered a stroke were motor disability—74.9%, including hemiparesis—63.7%, tetraparesis—25.8%, tetraplegia—10.4%, epilepsy—28%, disorders of speech—17.8%, cognitive and behavioral problems—53.9%.

Conclusions

In the acute period of the disease, patients had a wide range of clinical symptoms of IS, reflecting the patient's condition, from mild symptoms to severe forms of neuropsychomotor disorders, with predominantly mild or moderate forms in most patients—89 (82.4%) cases. The study enabled the elucidation of epidemiological peculiarities and stratification of clinical–paraclinical manifestations of ischemic stroke in children of different ages, as well as the determination of predictive clinical and paraclinical signs for this disease in newborns and children, and served as the basis for the development of prognostic algorithms for IS in newborns and children. These diagnostic algorithms will facilitate the correct approach of specialists in the field, which will contribute to the early diagnosis of stroke in children and newborns.

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